

Large-eddy simulation of primary atomization using an entropy stable conservative level set

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1 Introduction

The atomization process in applications of propulsion and power is commonly characterized by high pressure injections in complex geometries. The liquid undertakes a large acceleration during the expansion at the nozzle and breaks down into small pieces or filaments that eventually form droplets [1]. Vallet et al. (2001) [1] proposed an Eulerian model based on the application of concepts for turbulent mixing to flow atomization in the context of RANS. Based on this work, the model was updated with new closures and different modelling strategies [2, 3, 4] and extended to LES [5, 6]. Other modelling strategies for multiphase flow in LES have also been presented in the literature [7, 8, 9]. The use of large-eddy simulation (LES) is mandatory when modelling applications of industrial interest, as DNS at engine-realistic conditions is out of the scope even with current HPC systems from today. Nevertheless, DNS conditions have also been addressed in the literature at moderate Reynolds numbers [8, 10, 11]. The numerical discretization of two-phase flows poses several challenges in the modelling community, specially at high Reynolds and Weber numbers. Different discretization strategies can be found in the literature. Menard et al. (2007) [2] proposed a level set/VOF approach, Balcazar et al. (2014) [10] and Desjardins et al.(2013) [8] use a conservative level set with a re-initialization equation, while Vaudor et al. (2017) [11] introduce a consistent calculation of mass and momentum fluxes.

The present study proposes a numerical strategy for solving primary atomization using LES based on an entropy stable conservative level set method. The modelling approach includes an extension of the conservative level set equation stabilized with an entropy stable method (Guermond, 2017) [12] for the regions where the interface can be resolved, while it includes a subgrid contribution when the slip-velocity of

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the two-phase flow can not be resolved with the given filter size [5]. This modelling approach has been coupled to the transport equation of subgrid interphase surface density in order to predict primary atomization in a pure Eulerian framework. In the present work, continuous finite elements are used in order to enable the modelling of realistic geometries.

2 Mathematics

The modelling approach presented here is developed to describe primary atomization at high Weber and Reynolds number flows[1]. The system of equations is given by the conservation of momentum, liquid volume fraction ϕ , and liquid/gas interface Σ in the incompressible limit, with $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$. The system is closed by the equation of state for a liquid/gas mixture given by $\rho = \phi \rho_l + (1 - \phi) \rho_g$. The liquid/gas interface density Σ represents the quantity of liquid/gas interface per unit of volume and it is used to provide the characteristics and sizes of the liquid droplets in the dense part of the spray. The conservation equations will be presented below using spatially filtered quantities for LES. A decomposition of $\bar{\Sigma}$ following Chesnel et al. (2011) [5] is used and the subgrid surface density $\bar{\Sigma}'$ that evolves similar to $\bar{\Sigma}$ is solved instead. This separation is based on the existence of a minimum surface density $\bar{\Sigma}_{min}$ due to the presence of liquid and a subgrid surface density $\bar{\Sigma}'$ that evolves similar to $\bar{\Sigma}$.

$$\bar{\Sigma} = \bar{\Sigma}_{min} + \bar{\Sigma}' \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\Sigma}_{min}$ is obtained from empirical correlations based on DNS [5] and given by

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{min} = \frac{\alpha}{\Delta} \sqrt{\bar{\phi} (1 - \bar{\phi})} \quad (2)$$

with $\bar{\Delta}$ being a characteristic length scale (filter size in standard LES with implicit filtering) and $\alpha = 2.4$. Therefore, the transport equation for the liquid-gas interface can be expressed in terms of $\bar{\Sigma}'$ rather than $\bar{\Sigma}$.

The complete set of governing equations is presented here using filtered quantities and reads:

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{\rho}\tilde{\mathbf{u}})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\rho}\tilde{\mathbf{u}}\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) = \nabla \cdot (\mu + \mu_t)\nabla\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \cdot (\mu + \mu_t)(\nabla\tilde{\mathbf{u}})^T - \nabla\bar{p} + \sigma k\mathbf{n}\delta_\Gamma \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial\bar{\phi}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}}\bar{\phi}) = -\nabla \cdot \tau_\phi \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial\bar{\Sigma}'}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}}\bar{\Sigma}') = \nabla \cdot (\bar{\Sigma}'(\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_\Gamma)) + \dot{\bar{\Sigma}}_{int} \quad (5)$$

where the variables are expressed in standard notation.

The turbulent flux τ_ϕ and the slip velocity $\bar{\Sigma}'(\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_\Gamma)$ are both modelled using a gradient assumption closure [5, 6]. The source term $\dot{\bar{\Sigma}}_{int}$ represents the produc-

tion/destruction of surface density by the mean shear, turbulence and liquid structure interactions [5] and is modelled by

$$\dot{\bar{\Sigma}}_{int} = \frac{\bar{\Sigma}}{\tau_b} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{\Sigma}}{\bar{\Sigma}_{crit}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The equilibrium value of surface density $\bar{\Sigma}_{crit}$ is obtained from a critical Weber number expressed in terms of balance of turbulent kinetic energy and takes the form of

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{crit} = \bar{\Sigma}_{min} + \bar{\phi} (1 - \bar{\phi}) \frac{\bar{\rho} \bar{k}}{\sigma We_{crit}} \quad (7)$$

The spatial discretization is based on a low dissipation finite element method with an explicit algorithm of the fractional step to solve the velocity/pressure coupling [14] and an entropy stable conservative level set (Guermond, 2017) [12] for the volume fraction equation. The main difference with Guermond work is the use of a cell-based viscosity instead of an edge-based version. The temporal discretization is based on a third order energy preserving Runge-Kutta scheme.

3 Results

3.1 Validation

In order to validate the proposed interface tracking algorithm, the single vortex deformation of a circle is considered. Three regular Q_1 meshes are considered in the validation (**m1**: 100x100, **m2**: 200x200 and **m3**: 400x400). Mass conservation is preserved in the three levels of mesh, being the L2 error for all cases below 10^{-6} . In figure 1, snapshots for $t = 2$ and $t = 3$ and **m3** mesh are presented. Results are similar to the ones presented by Guermond et al. (2017) using entropy stable edge based viscosity instead of our proposed cell based viscosity. Therefore, we can conclude that the proposed extension of the initial Guermond methodology to cell based viscosity, results in similar performance but on a more general numerical framework easier to merge with subgrid scale models for LES.

Fig. 1 Single vortex deformation of a circle using 400x400 nodes at $t = 2$ s (left) and $t = 3$ s (right).

3.2 Turbulent jet

The application considered to address the presented modelling approach is a test case representative of primary atomization. The configuration was proposed by Menard et al. (2007) and has been the subject of some investigations [5, 6]. The test case corresponds to a liquid jet issuing into a quiescent air at moderate pressure. Two unstructured meshes composed by tetrahedrons with local refinement regions of $5 \mu m$ and $3 \mu m$ ending in 10 million and 60 million cells respectively are tested. A turbulent inlet velocity with a prescribed velocity profile [2] is imposed using fluctuations generated by diffusion [13]. A length scale of 10% and 20% of the jet diameter are used for the coarse and fine mesh respectively.

The evolution of the flow can be distinguished in Fig. 2 by an iso-surface of the volume fraction and a contour plot of volume fraction along the spanwise direction. It is observed the atomization of jet with the main liquid core surrounded by a cloud of droplets and how the smallest droplets are formed at the front of the jet. After 510 diameters, the jet starts to break and filaments are generated.

Fig. 2 Instantaneous snapshot of iso-contour (top) and contour plot over central plane (bottom) of volume fraction from a P_1 grid with 60 M cells after $45 \mu s$ of injection.

The results are time-integrated and compared with the DNS data from Menard et al. [2]. The data for comparison includes the liquid volume fraction and surface density. As the surface density equation results are sensitive to the initial and boundary conditions, the solutions from DNS and the present LES are scaled by Σ_0 [5]. The liquid dispersion and surface density compared to the DNS data along the centreline is shown in Fig. 3(a). The results indicate a good level of correlation with the DNS data for the two meshes tested. The penetration is well captured and the results show the influence of resolution on the jet decay. The results show similar liquid core length, but different dispersion. The surface density distribution is also

rather similar along the centreline. The dispersion of the liquid can be distinguished in Fig. 3(b). At the two upstream locations ($x/D=5$, and $x/D=10$), the results are in good agreement and the fine mesh shows better predictions than the coarse mesh in terms of liquid dispersion. The predictions of surface density show a similar behaviour for the two cases, which suggests a further revision of the critical Weber number would be recommended and is left for future work. At downstream conditions, the results on the finest mesh show high penetration and lower decay of the liquid core, that in turns affects the surface density.

Fig. 3 Mean liquid volume fraction and surface density along the centreline (left) and radial distributions at three axial locations (middle and right): $x/D=5$ (top), $x/D=10$ (middle) and $x/D=20$ (bottom).

4 Conclusions

The present study proposes a numerical strategy for solving primary atomization using LES based on an entropy stable conservative level set method. The modelling approach includes an extension of the conservative level set equation stabilized with an entropy stable method for the regions where the interface can be resolved, while it includes a subgrid contribution when the slip-velocity of the two-phase flow can not be resolved with the given filter size. This strategy has been applied to the study of primary breakup of a turbulent jet at moderate Re and We numbers using two levels of resolution. The results indicate the present approach is able to reproduce the liquid penetration and dispersion, and the comparison with the reference data from DNS is satisfactory.

Acknowledgements This work has been partially financially supported by the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad, Secretaría de Estado de Investigación, Desarrollo e Innovación, Spain

(Ref. TRA2017-89139-C2-2-R, CHEST) and by the Clean Sky Program from European Unions Horizon 2020 H2020-CS2-CFP06-2017-01 Fire Extinction ID: 785549. We also acknowledge Red Espanola de Surpercomputación (RES) for awarding us access to the MareNostrum IV (FI-2019-1-0019 and IM-2019-2-0012), and Juan de la Cierva personal grant IJCI-2015-26686..

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